

Some More 4-Prime Cordial Graphs

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Abstract: Let G be a (p, q) graph, $H \prec G$ and $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ be a map. For each edge uv , assign the label $\gcd(f(u), f(v))$. Then, f is called Smarandachely k -prime cordial labeling on G to H if $|v_f^H(i) - v_f^H(j)| \leq 1$, $i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ and $|e_f^H(0) - e_f^H(1)| \leq 1$, but there exist integers $0 \leq i \neq j \leq k$ such that $|v_f^{G \setminus H}(i) - v_f^{G \setminus H}(j)| \geq 2$, or $|e_f^{G \setminus H}(0) - e_f^{G \setminus H}(1)| \geq 2$, where $v_f^H(x)$, $v_f^{G \setminus H}(x)$ respectively denotes the numbers of vertices of H , $G \setminus H$ labeled with x , $e_f^H(1)$, $e_f^H(0)$ and $e_f^{G \setminus H}(1)$, $e_f^{G \setminus H}(0)$ respectively denote the number of edges labeled with 1 and not labeled with 1 in H , $G \setminus H$. Particularly, a Smarandachely k -prime cordial labeling on G to G is called k -prime cordial labeling with $v_f(x)$, $e_f(1)$ and $e_f(0)$ replacing notations $v_f^H(x)$, $e_f^H(1)$ and $e_f^H(0)$ for abbreviation. A graph with a k -prime cordial labeling is called a k -prime cordial graph. In this paper we investigate 4-prime cordial labeling behavior of lotus inside a circle, sunflower graph, $S(K_2 + mK_1)$, $S(P_n \odot K_1)$, dodecahedron, and some more graphs.

Key Words: Smarandachely k -prime labelling, k -prime labelling, cycle, wheel, join, sunflower graph, lotus inside a circle.

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§1. Introduction

In this paper graphs are finite, simple and undirected. Let G be a (p, q) graph where p refers the number of vertices of G and q refers the number of edge of G . The number of vertices of a graph G is called order of G , and the number of edges is called size of G . In 1987, Cahit introduced the concept of cordial labeling of graphs [1]. Sundaram, Ponraj, Somasundaram [5] have introduced the notion of prime cordial labeling of graphs. Also they discussed the prime cordial labeling behavior of various graphs. Recently Ponraj et al. [7], introduced k -prime cordial labeling of graphs. They have studied 3-prime cordiality of several graphs in [7, 8]. In [9, 10] Ponraj et al. studied the 4-prime cordial labeling behavior of complete graph,

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book, flower, mC_n , wheel, gear, double cone, helm, closed helm, butterfly graph, and friendship graph and some more graphs. In this paper we have studied about the 4-prime cordiality of lotus inside a circle, sunflower graph and some more graphs. Let x be any real number. Then $\lfloor x \rfloor$ stands for the largest integer less than or equal to x and $\lceil x \rceil$ stands for smallest integer greater than or equal to x . Terms not defined here follow from Harary [3] and Gallian [2].

§2. Preliminaries

Remark 2.1([6]) A 2-prime cordial labeling is a product cordial labeling.

Remark 2.2([5]) A p -prime cordial labeling is a prime cordial labeling.

Definition 2.3 The join of two graphs $G_1 + G_2$ is obtained from G_1 and G_2 and whose vertex set is $V(G_1 + G_2) = V(G_1) \cup V(G_2)$ and edge set $E(G_1 + G_2) = E(G_1) \cup E(G_2) \cup \{uv : u \in V(G_1), v \in V(G_2)\}$.

Definition 2.4 The graph $C_n + K_1$ is called a wheel. In a wheel, the vertex of degree n is called the central vertex and the vertices on the cycle C_n are called rim vertices.

Definition 2.5 The sunflower graph SF_n is obtained by taking a wheel with central vertex u and the cycle $C_n : u_1u_2 \cdots u_nu_1$ and new vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n where v_i is joined by vertices $u_i, u_{i+1 \pmod n}$.

Definition 2.6 The lotus inside a circle LC_n is a graph obtained from the cycle $C_n : v_1v_2 \cdots v_nv_1$ and a star $K_{1,n}$ with central vertex u and the end vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n by joining each u_i to v_i and $v_{i+1 \pmod n}$.

Definition 2.7 The subdivision graph $S(G)$ of a graph G is obtained by replacing each edge uv by a path uwv .

Definition 2.8 The graph P_n^2 is obtained from the path P_n by adding edges that joins all vertices u and v with $d(u, v) = 2$.

Definition 2.9 Let G_1, G_2 respectively be $(p_1, q_1), (p_2, q_2)$ graphs. The corona of G_1 with G_2 , $G_1 \odot G_2$ is the graph obtained by taking one copy of G_1 and p_1 copies of G_2 and joining the i^{th} vertex of G_1 with an edge to every vertex in the i^{th} copy of G_2 .

Definition 2.10 The one-point union of t copies of the cycle C_3 is called a friendship graph $C_3^{(t)}$.

Definition 2.11 The DH_n is a graph with vertex set $V(DH_n) = \{u_i, v_i, x_i, y_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and the edge set $E(DH_n) = \{uu_{i+1}, y_iv_{i+1}, x_ix_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_iv_i, v_iy_i, x_iy_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_1u_n, y_nv_1, x_1x_n\}$. DH_5 is called a Tetrahedron.

Definition 2.12 The Cartesian product graph $G_1 \square G_2$ is defined as follows: Consider any two points $u = (u_1, u_2)$ and $v = (v_1, v_2)$ in $V = V_1 \times V_2$. Then u and v are adjacent in $G_1 \square G_2$

whenever $[u_1 = v_1 \text{ and } u_2v_2 \in E(G_2)]$ or $[u_2 = v_2 \text{ and } u_1v_1 \in E(G_1)]$.

Definition 2.13 A ladder L_n is the graph $P_n \times P_2$. Let $V(L_n) = \{u_i, v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(L_n) = \{u_iu_{i+1}, v_iv_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_iv_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_1u_n, v_1v_n\}$.

The graph GL_n is obtained from the ladder L_n with $V(GL_n) = V(L_n)$ and $E(GL_n) = E(L_n) \cup \{u_iv_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}$.

Theorem 2.14([7]) The cycle C_n , $n \neq 3$ is k -prime cordial where k is even.

§3. Main Results

3.1 Cycle Related Graphs

Theorem 3.1 The lotus inside a circle LC_n is 4-prime cordial if and only if $n > 4$.

Proof Note that the order and size of LC_n are $2n+1$ and $4n$ respectively. Suppose $n = 3$ or 4 then one can easily check that there does not exist a 4-prime cordial labeling and so we assume $n > 4$. Here we divide the proof into four cases.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

We construct a labeling f as follows: assign the label 4 to the vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{\frac{n}{2}}$ then put the label 3 to the vertex $v_{\frac{n}{2}+1}$. The remaining vertices of the cycle, namely, $v_{\frac{n}{2}+2}, v_{\frac{n}{2}+3}, \dots, v_n$ are labeled by 1. Now we consider the center of the star u . The vertex u is labeled by 2. For the vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n , first we consider the vertices u_{n-1} and u_n . Assign the labels 1, 2 respectively to the vertices u_{n-1} and u_n . Consider the vertices $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{n}{2}-1}$. Fix the label 2 to this vertices. Then the vertices $u_{\frac{n}{2}}, u_{\frac{n}{2}+1}, \dots, u_{n-2}$ are labeled by 3.

Case 2. $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

Assign the labels to the vertices $u, u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n-3, v_j, 1 \leq j \leq n-1$ as in case 1. The assign the labels 3, 1, 2 to the vertices u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}, u_n respectively. Finally we assign the label 4 to the vertex v_n .

Case 3. $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

Assign the label 4 to the vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{\frac{n}{2}}$. For the vertex $v_{\frac{n}{2}+1}$ we assign the number 3. The remaining vertices of the cycle from $v_{\frac{n}{2}+2}, v_{\frac{n}{2}+3}, \dots, v_n$ receives the label 1. Put the label 2 to the vertex u . Now we consider the vertices $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$. Assign the label 2 to the vertices u_n, u_i where $1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2}-1$, then assign the integer 3 to the vertices $u_{\frac{n}{2}}, u_{\frac{n}{2}+1}, \dots, u_{n-2}$. Finally we assign the label 1 to the vertex u_{n-1} .

Case 4. $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

First we consider the vertices of the cycle. The label 4 is used to the vertices $v_i, 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2}$. Put the label 3 to the vertex $v_{\frac{n+3}{2}}$. The unlabeled vertices of the cycle are now labeled by 1. Then put the number 2 to the vertex u . If we consider the vertices $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$, we assign the label 2 to the vertices u_j where $1 \leq j \leq \frac{n-1}{2}$ then assign 3 to the vertices $u_{\frac{n+1}{2}}, \dots, u_{n-1}$.

Finally put the number 1 to the vertex u_n . □

The following Table 1 establish that the above mentioned labeling f is a 4-prime cordial labeling.

Values of n	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	$e_f(0)$	$e_f(1)$
$n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\lfloor \frac{2n+1}{4} \rfloor$	$\lceil \frac{2n+1}{4} \rceil$	$\lfloor \frac{2n+1}{4} \rfloor$	$\lfloor \frac{2n+1}{4} \rfloor$	$2n$	$2n$
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	$\lfloor \frac{2n+1}{4} \rfloor$	$\lceil \frac{2n+1}{4} \rceil$	$\lceil \frac{2n+1}{4} \rceil$	$\lceil \frac{2n+1}{4} \rceil$	$2n$	$2n$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\lfloor \frac{2n+1}{4} \rfloor$	$\lceil \frac{2n+1}{4} \rceil$	$\lfloor \frac{2n+1}{4} \rfloor$	$\lfloor \frac{2n+1}{4} \rfloor$	$2n$	$2n$
$n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	$\lfloor \frac{2n+1}{4} \rfloor$	$\lceil \frac{2n+1}{4} \rceil$	$\lceil \frac{2n+1}{4} \rceil$	$\lceil \frac{2n+1}{4} \rceil$	$2n$	$2n$

Table 1

Theorem 3.2 *The sunflower graph SF_n is 4-prime cordial for all n .*

Proof First we observe that the order and size of SF_n are $2n + 1$ and $4n$ respectively. We consider the following cases.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{n}{4}}$. Then put the number 4 to the next consecutive vertices $u_{\frac{n}{4}+1}, \dots, u_{\frac{n}{2}+1}$. The next vertex $u_{\frac{n}{2}+2}$ is labeled by 3. Then the remaining vertices of the cycle, namely, $u_{\frac{n}{2}+3}, \dots, u_n$ are labeled by 1. For the central vertex u , we use the label 2. We now move to the vertices $v_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$. Assign the label 2 to the vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{\frac{n}{4}-1}$. Then assign the label 4 to the vertices $v_{\frac{n}{4}}, v_{\frac{n}{4}+1}, \dots, v_{\frac{n}{2}-1}$. The next three vertices $v_{\frac{n}{2}}, v_{\frac{n}{2}+1}, v_{\frac{n}{4}+2}$ are labeled by 1, 3, 1 respectively. Finally the remaining unlabeled vertices received the integer 3.

Case 2. $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

First we consider the vertices of the cycle C_n . For the vertices $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{n-5}{4}}$, we assign the label 2. The successive vertices $u_{\frac{n-1}{4}}, \dots, u_{\frac{n-1}{2}}$ are labeled by 4. Put the label 3 to the vertex $u_{\frac{n+1}{2}}$. The vertices $u_{\frac{n+3}{2}}, \dots, u_{n-1}$ are labeled by 1. Put the label 2 to the vertex u_n . Then assign the label 2 to the central vertex u . We now move to the vertices $v_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$. Assign the label 2 to the vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{\frac{n-5}{4}}$. Then put the number 4 to the vertices $v_{\frac{n-1}{4}}, \dots, v_{\frac{n-3}{2}}$. Put the labels 3, 3, 1 respectively to the vertices $v_{\frac{n-1}{2}}, v_{\frac{n+1}{2}}$. Assign the label 3 to the vertices $v_{\frac{n+3}{2}}, \dots, v_{n-1}$. Finally we assign the number 2 to v_n .

Case 3. $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

We first consider the vertex u . Label it by 2. Then we consider the vertices of the cycle C_n . Assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{n+2}{4}}$. Then put the integer 4 to the vertices $u_{\frac{n+6}{4}}, \dots, u_{\frac{n+2}{2}}$. The next vertex $u_{\frac{n+4}{2}}$ is labeled by 3. The remaining vertices of the cycle are labeled by 1. Then consider the vertices $v_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$. Assign the label 2 to the vertices v_i where $1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-2}{4}$ then the vertices $v_{\frac{n-2}{4}+i}$ where $1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-2}{4}$ are labeled with 4. Put the labels 1, 3, 1 to the next consecutive vertices $v_{\frac{n}{2}}, v_{\frac{n+2}{2}}, v_{\frac{n+4}{2}}$. Finally put the number 3 for the unlabeled vertices.

Case 4. $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

Assign the label 2 to the vertices u_i , where $1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{4}$, then assign 4 to the vertices $u_{\frac{n+1}{4}+i}$ where $1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{4}$. The next vertex $u_{\frac{n+3}{2}}$ received the label 3. Then assign the label 1 to the remaining vertices of the cycle. Put the integer 2 to the vertex u . Then we consider the vertices v_i , $1 \leq i \leq n$. Assign the number 2 to the vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{\frac{n-3}{4}}$. Then assign 4 to the vertices $v_{\frac{n+1}{4}}, \dots, v_{\frac{n-1}{2}}$. The next two consecutive vertices $v_{\frac{n+1}{2}}, v_{\frac{n+3}{2}}$ are labeled by 3, 1 respectively. The rest of the unlabeled vertices are labeled by 3.

The Table 2 shows that the above labeling f is a required 4-prime cordial labeling. \square

Values of n	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	$e_f(0)$	$e_f(1)$
$n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$\frac{n}{2} + 1$	$2n$	$2n$
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n-1}{2}$	$\frac{n+1}{2}$	$\frac{n+1}{2}$	$\frac{n+1}{2}$	$2n$	$2n$
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$\frac{n}{2} + 1$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$\frac{n}{2}$	$2n$	$2n$
$n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{n-1}{2}$	$\frac{n+1}{2}$	$\frac{n+1}{2}$	$\frac{n+1}{2}$	$2n$	$2n$

Table 2

A 4-prime cordial labeling of SF_8 is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Theorem 3.3 DH_n is 4-prime cordial.

Proof Clearly DH_n consists of $4n$ vertices and $6n$ edges. We now give the label to the vertices of DH_n as follows: Assign the label 2 to the vertices u_i , $1 \leq i \leq n$ and assign the label 4 to the vertices v_i , $1 \leq i \leq n$. Now we move to the vertices y_i . Assign the label 1 to the vertices y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n . Finally assign the label 3 to the vertices x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n . This vertex labeling f is obviously a 4-prime cordial labeling of DH_n . Since, $v_f(1) = v_f(2) = v_f(3) = v_f(4) = n$ and $e_f(0) = e_f(1) = 3n$. \square

Theorem 3.4 Let C_n be the cycle $u_1u_2 \dots u_nu_1$. Let G_n be the graph with $V(G_n) = V(C_n) \cup \{v_i :$

$1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(G_n) = E(C_n) \cup \{u_i v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_{i+1} v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}$. Then G_n is 4-prime cordial for all $n \neq 4$.

Proof Clearly for any vertex labeling of G_4 , the maximum possible edges with label 0 is 4. Hence G_4 is not 4-prime cordial.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, $n \neq 4$.

Let $n = 4t$. Assign the label 2 to the vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{2t} and 4 to the vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2t} . Next assign the label 3 to the vertices u_{2t+1}, u_{2t+2} and u_{2t+3} . Next assign the label 1 to the cycle vertices $u_{2t+4}, u_{2t+6}, \dots, u_{4t}$ and 3 to the vertices $v_{2t+4}, v_{2t+5}, \dots, v_{4t-1}, v_{4t}$. Finally assign the remaining non labeled vertices by 1.

Case 2. $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

Let $n = 4t + 1$. In this case, assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{2t+1}$ and 4 to the vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2t+1}$. Next assign the label 1 to the cycle vertices $u_{2t+2}, u_{2t+3}, \dots$ and u_{4t+1} . Finally assign the label 3 to the non labeled vertices $v_{2t+2}, v_{2t+3}, \dots, v_{4t+1}$.

Case 3. $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

Let $n = 4t + 2$. In this case we assign the label 2 to the vertices u_i ($1 \leq i \leq 2t + 1$) and 4 to the vertices v_i ($1 \leq i \leq 2t + 1$). Next assign the label 3 to the cycle vertices u_{2t+2}, u_{2t+3} and u_{2t+4} . Now we assign the label 1 to the vertices $u_{2t+5}, u_{2t+6}, \dots, u_{4t+2}$. Next assign the label 3 to the vertices $v_{4t+2}, v_{4t+1}, \dots, v_{2t+4}$. Finally assign the label to the non labeled vertices by 1.

Case 4. $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

Let $n = 4t + 3$. Assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{2t+2}$ and 4 to the vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2t+2}$. Next assign the label 1 to the vertices $u_{2t+3}, u_{2t+4}, \dots, u_{4t+3}$. Finally assign the label to the vertices $v_{2t+3}, v_{2t+4}, \dots, v_{4t+3}$.

Hence the vertex labeling given above is obviously a 4-prime cordial labeling of G_n . \square

3.2 Subdivided Graphs

Theorem 3.5 $S(K_2 + mK_1)$ is 4-prime cordial.

Proof Let $V(S(K_2 + mK_1)) = \{u, v, w, u_i, v_i, w_i : 1 \leq i \leq m\}$ and $E(S(K_2 + mK_1)) = \{uv, vw, uu_i, u_i w_i, w_i v_i, v_i u : 1 \leq i \leq m\}$. Note that $S(K_2 + mK_1)$ has $3m + 3$ vertices and $4m + 2$ edges. The proof is divided into four cases depending upon the nature of n .

Case 1. $n = 4t$.

Assign the label 2 to the vertex u . Next assign the label 2 to the vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{3t} . We now assign the label 4 to the vertices $u_{3t+1}, u_{3t+2}, \dots, u_{4t}$. Next we move to the vertices w_i . Assign the label 4 to the vertices w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{2t} . Next assign 3 to the vertices $w_{3t+1}, w_{3t+2}, \dots, w_{4t}$. Next assign the label 3 to the vertices $v_{4t}, v_{4-1}, \dots, v_{3t+1}$. We now assign the labels 4, 3 respectively to the vertices w, v . Finally, assign 1 to all the remaining non labeled vertices.

Case 2. $n = 4t + 1$.

Assign the labels to the vertices $u_i, v_i, w_i, 1 \leq i \leq 4t + 1, u, v, w$ as in case 1. Finally assign 2, 4 and 1 respectively to the vertices u_{4t+1}, w_{4t+1} and v_{4t+1} .

Case 3. $n = 4t + 2$.

As in Case 2, assign the labels to the vertices $u_i, v_i, w_i, 1 \leq i \leq 4t + 1, u, v, w$. Next assign the labels 2, 1, 3 to the vertices u_{4t+2}, w_{4t+2} and v_{4t+2} respectively.

Case 4. $n = 4t + 3$.

Assign the labels to the vertices $u_i, v_i, w_i, 1 \leq i \leq 4t + 2, u, v, w$ as in case 3. Finally assign 4, 1, 3 respectively to the vertices u_{4t+3}, w_{4t+3} and v_{4t+3} .

Clearly, the above labeling is a 4-prime cordial labeling of $S(K_2 + mK_1)$. \square

Theorem 3.6 $S(P_n \odot K_1)$ is 4-prime cordial.

Proof Let P_n be the path $u_1u_2 \dots u_n$ and $V(P_n \odot K_1) = V(P_n) \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$, $E(P_n \odot K_1) = E(P_n) \cup \{u_iv_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. The graph $S(P_n \odot K_1)$ is obtained by subdividing the edge u_iu_{i+1} with w_i and the edge u_iv_i with x_i . Note that $S(P_n \odot K_1)$ has $4n - 1$ vertices and $4n - 2$ edges. The proof is divided into four cases.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Let $n = 4t$. Assign the label 2 to the vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{4t} and 4 to the vertices $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{4t-1}$ and x_1 . We now assign the label 1 to the vertices x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{4t} . Finally assign the label 3 to the pendent vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{4t} .

Case 2. $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

Assign the label to the vertices $u_i, v_i, x_i (1 \leq i \leq n - 1)$ and $w_i (1 \leq i \leq n - 2)$ as in Case 1. Finally assign the labels 2, 4, 3 and 1 respectively to the vertices w_{n-1}, u_n, x_n, v_n .

Case 3. $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 2, assign the label to the vertices $u_i, v_i, x_i (1 \leq i \leq n - 1)$ and $w_i (1 \leq i \leq n - 2)$. Next assign the labels 2, 4, 3 and 1 to the vertices w_{n-1}, u_n, x_n, v_n respectively.

Case 4. $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

In this case also assign labels to the vertices except w_{n-1}, u_n, x_n, v_n as in case 3. Then assign the labels 2, 4, 3 and 1 to the vertices w_{n-1}, u_n, x_n, v_n respectively.

Clearly, the vertex labeling given in all cases is a 4-prime cordial labeling of $S(P_n \odot K_1)$. \square

Theorem 3.7 $S(C_3^{(t)})$ is 4-prime cordial.

Proof Note that $S(C_3^{(t)}) \equiv C_6^{(t)}$. Let the i^{th} copy of the C_6 be $u_1^i u_2^i u_3^i u_4^i u_5^i u_6^i$, where $1 \leq i \leq t$ and $u_1^1 = u_1^2 = u_1^3 = u_1^4 = u_1^5 = u_1^6$.

Case 1. t is even, $t \geq 4$.

Assign the label 2 to the central vertex.

Subcase 1.1 $t \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Assign the label 2 to all the vertices of first $\frac{t}{4}$ copies of the cycle C_5 . Next we move to the $(\frac{t}{4} + 1)^{th}$ copy. Assign the label 4 to all the vertices of the $(\frac{t}{4} + 1)^{th}, (\frac{t}{4} + 2)^{th}, \dots, (\frac{t}{2})^{th}$ copies of the cycle C_5 . We now consider the $(\frac{t}{2} + 1)^{th}$ copy. Assign the label 1 and 3 alternatively to the vertices of the $(\frac{t}{2} + 1)^{th}$ copy of the cycle. In a similar fashion assign the label 1 and 3 alternatively to the vertices of the $(\frac{t}{2} + 2)^{th}, \dots, t^{th}$ copy of the cycle C_5 .

Subcase 1.2 $t \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

In this case assign the label 2 to all the vertices of first $\frac{t-2}{4}$ copies of the cycle C_5 . Now consider the $(\frac{t+2}{4})^{th}$ copy. Assign the label 4 to all the vertices of the cycle $(\frac{t+2}{4})^{th}$ copy. Similarly assign the label 4 to the $(\frac{t+6}{4})^{th}, \dots, (\frac{t-2}{2})^{th}$ copies of the cycle C_5 . We now move to the $(\frac{t}{2})^{th}$ copy. In this copy, assign the label 2 to the vertices u_2^t, u_3^t and 4 to the vertices u_4^t, u_5^t, u_6^t . Next assign 1, 3 alternatively to the vertices of the $(\frac{t}{2} + 1)^{th}, \dots, t^{th}$ copies of the cycle.

Case 2. t is odd.

Subcase 2.1 $t \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

As in subcase 1a, assign the label to the vertices of all the $i^{th}, 1 \leq i \leq t - 1$ copies of C_5 . In the last copy, assign the labels 2, 4, 4, 1 and 3 respectively to the vertices $u_2^t, u_3^t, u_4^t, u_5^t$ and u_6^t .

Subcase 2.2 $t \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

Assign the label to the vertices of $(t - 1)$ copies of the cycle as in subcase 1b. Finally, assign the labels 2, 4, 3, 3 and 1 to the vertices $u_2^t, u_3^t, u_4^t, u_5^t$ and u_6^t respectively.

The Table 3 establish that the above vertex labeling f is a 4-prime cordial labeling of $S(C_3^{(t)}), t \geq 4$.

Nature of t	$v_f(1)$	$v_f(2)$	$v_f(3)$	$v_f(4)$	$e_f(0)$	$e_f(1)$
$t \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{5t}{4}$	$\frac{5t}{4} + 1$	$\frac{5t}{4}$	$\frac{5t}{4}$	$3t$	$3t$
$t \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{5t-1}{4}$	$\frac{5t+3}{4}$	$\frac{5t-1}{4}$	$\frac{5t+3}{4}$	$3t$	$3t$
$t \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{5t+2}{4}$	$\frac{5t+2}{4}$	$\frac{5t-2}{4}$	$\frac{5t+2}{4}$	$3t$	$3t$
$t \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	$\frac{5t+1}{4}$	$\frac{5t+1}{4}$	$\frac{5t+1}{4}$	$\frac{5t+1}{4}$	$3t$	$3t$

Table 3

$S(C_3^{(1)}) \cong C_6$ is 4-prime cordial follows from Theorem 2.14. The 4-prime cordial labelings of $S(C_3^{(2)})$ and $S(C_3^{(3)})$ are given in Figure 2. □

Figure 2

3.3 Miscellaneous Graphs

Theorem 3.8 P_n^2 is 4-prime cordial if and only if $n \neq 4$.

Proof Let P_n be the path u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n . Clearly, the order and size of P_n^2 are n and $2n - 3$ respectively. It is easy to verify that P_4^2 does not admits a 4-rime cordial labeling. Let us assume that $n \neq 4$.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Let $n = 4t$. Assign the label 1 to the vertices $u_1, u_3, \dots, u_{2t-1}$. Next assign the label 3 to the vertices u_2, u_4, \dots, u_{2t} . Assign the label 2 to the next t vertices u_{2t+1}, \dots, u_{3t} . Finally, assign the label 4 to the next t non labeled vertices u_{3t+1}, \dots, u_{4t} .

Case 2. $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

Subcase 2.1 $n \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$.

Assign the labels to the vertices of $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$ as in Case 1. Finally, assign the label 2 to the vertex u_n .

Subcase 2.1 $n \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$.

As in Case 1, assign the labels to the vertices $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$. Then assign the label 1 to the vertex u_n .

Case 3. $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

Subcase 3.1 $n \equiv 2 \pmod{8}$.

Assign the labels to the vertices of $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$ as in Subcase 2.1. Then assign the label 1 to the vertex u_n .

Subcase 3.2 $n \equiv 6 \pmod{8}$.

As in Case 1, assign the labels to the vertices $u_i, 1 \leq i \leq n - 2$. Then assign the labels 2 and 1 respectively to the vertices u_{n-1} and u_n .

Case 4. $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

Subcase 4.1 $n \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$.

As in Subcase 3.1, assign the labels to the vertices of u_i , $1 \leq i \leq n-1$. Finally, assign the label 4 to the last vertex u_n .

Subcase 4b. $n \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$.

Assign the labels to the vertices u_i , $1 \leq i \leq n-1$ as in Subcase 3.2. Finally, assign the label 4 to the vertex u_n .

It is easy to verify that the above vertex labeling pattern is 4-prime cordial labeling. \square

The following Figure 3 is an example of a 4-prime cordial labeling of P_{10}^2 .

Figure 3

Theorem 3.9 *The graph GL_n is 4-prime cordial for $n > 2$.*

Proof Here we consider the following cases.

Case 1. $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Clearly GL_n has $2n$ vertices and $4n-3$ edges. Let $n = 4t$. Assign the label 2 to the vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{2t} and assign the label 4 to the vertices $v_2, v_3, \dots, v_{2t+1}$. Next assign the labels 3, 1 alternatively to the vertices to the vertices $u_{2t+1}, u_{2t+2}, \dots, u_{4t}$. Assign the label 1 to the vertices $v_{4t}, v_{4t-2}, v_{4t-4}, \dots, v_{2t+5}$ and assign the label 3 to the vertices $v_{4t-1}, v_{4t-3}, v_{4t-5}, \dots, v_{2t+4}$. Finally assign the labels 1, 1, 3 and 3 respectively to the vertices $v_{2t+3}, v_{2t+2}, v_{2t+1}$ and v_1 .

Case 2. $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

Assign the label to the vertices u_i, v_i , $1 \leq i \leq n-1$ as in case 1. Next assign the labels 2, 4 to the vertices u_n, v_n respectively.

Case 3. $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 2, assign the label to the vertices u_i, v_i , $1 \leq i \leq n-1$. Next assign the labels 1, 3 respectively to the vertices u_n, v_n . Finally interchange the labels of u_{2t+2} and u_{2t+3} , that is the label of u_{2t+2} is 3 and the label of u_{2t+3} is 1.

Case 4. $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 3, assign the label to the vertices u_i, v_i , $1 \leq i \leq n-1$. Then assign the labels 2, 4 to the vertices u_n, v_n respectively. Clearly the above vertex labeling is a 4 prime cordial labeling of GL_n for all $n \geq 4$ and $n \neq 2$. A 4-prime cordial labeling of GL_3 is shown in the following Figure 4. \square

Figure 4

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